

Technical Brief: Functional Prototype 1

Athens, Greece

Responsible

Partner

Capture and Utilisation of CO₂ from a biofuels biorefinery that include biomass combustion, ethanolic fermentation and anaerobic digestion via autotrophic algae growth

Production Line

Ethanol Fermentation
Biodiesel Production
Anaerobic Digestion

Biogenic Gas CO₂

End-Product

Bioethanol
Biodiesel
Biomass

Technologies

Enzymatic Capture of CO₂
Autotrophic Algae Cultivation

Performance Indicators

CO₂ capture efficiency target	≥ 85%
Microalgae Growth Target CO ₂ uptake Biomass	20-40g CO₂/m²/day 10-20g dry weight/m²/day
Bioenergy efficiency 1 (%BE₁) <small>Energy content of produced biofuels</small> <small>Energy input in the whole system</small>	81.66%
Bioenergy efficiency 2 (%BE₂) <small>Energy content of produced biofuels</small> <small>Energy content of initial feedstock</small>	81.67%
Biomass resource utilization (%BR) <small>kg products</small> <small>kg initial feedstock</small>	86.45%

Targets

- CO₂ Dissolution (orange unit): Using digestate (green tank), potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃), and carbonic anhydrase (CA) enzymes to dissolve CO₂ into an aqueous medium.
- Algae Cultivation: The CO₂-enriched solution is used in 4 raceway ponds (right side) to grow microalgae.
- Biomass Valorization: Algal biomass is harvested using sedimentation tanks (middle tanks) and then processed in the biorefinery to produce biofuels and extract CA for reuse.

Technical sketch

